

EU Fire Projects United

Joint Newsletter

#EUFireProjectsUnited

What is EUFireProjectsUnited?

Firelogue is an EU Coordination and Support Action (CSA) which connects the three EU Innovation Actions (IAs / TREEADS - SILVANUS - FIRE RES) and supports them by integrating their results across all stakeholders and phases of Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) and to connect them with existing insights from projects such as FirEUrisk

Firelogue's main goal is to unite as many fire-related projects as possible and to identify fields for collaboration. So, Firelogue's first effort is to create common dissemination actions with the IAs and other fire related projects. #EUFireProjectsUnited consists of Firelogue, SILVANUS, TREEADS, FIRE-RES, FirEUrisk, SAFERS, FIRElinks and FIRE-IN.

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What's new?

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What is Firelogue about?

Firelogue is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded under the Green Deal to support the clustering and cooperation among the projects, the integration of research results and the extensive and structured knowledge exchange to finally ensure that the demonstration of innovative and integrated approaches fulfils the expected impacts.

The cooperation on these topics have been agreed upon by the projects in a joint roadmap defining activities until 2025. The roadmap builds on a Clustering Event between the EU Fire projects that had been organised digitally in April 2022.

Firelogue

What are the results of the Firelogue project so far?

Firelogue therefore facilitates strategic cooperation between the projects along the following topics:

- Impact Assessment (towards Green Deal 2030 targets)
- Research Integration (Fuel Maps, Fire Event database, others)
- Knowledge Management on research results and WFRM practices
- Case study collaboration and exchange
- (Technical) exploitation | legacy uptake
- Communication & Dissemination incl. joint Events

In addition, Firelogue is currently developing five thematic working groups which will integrate the recommendations of the research projects and translate them into policy recommendations at EU level. The working groups encompass the following topics which can be reached via functional email addresses in case experts interested to contribute:

- Environment/Ecology: environ@firelogue.eu
- Societal aspects: society@firelogue.eu
- Civil Protection: civil-protection@firelogue.eu
- Insurance: insurance@firelogue.eu
- Infrastructure: infrastructure@firelogue.eu

The working groups are envisaged to contribute among others to the following policies: EU Forestry Strategy, EU Bioeconomy Strategy, EU Adaptation Strategy, Civil Protection Policies (rescEU) as well as policy instruments and networks such as the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre or the European Forest Information Service.

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What is the FIRE-RES project about?

FIRE-RES is a Horizon 2020 project that aims to boost the socio-ecological transition of the European Union towards a fire-resilient continent by developing a stream of innovation actions. FIRE-RES brings together a consortium formed by researchers, emergency-response bodies, technological companies, industry and civil society from 13 European countries and Chile.

To achieve its objective, the project developed a holistic and integrated fire management strategy to efficiently and effectively address Extreme Wildfire Events in Europe in 11 Living Labs thanks to its Innovation Actions.

Project members had the opportunity to meet twice: during the Kick-off meeting held in January 2022 in Solsona, Spain and during the 1st General Assembly in Wageningen, The Netherlands. During these days, partners could present and discuss their innovation actions and how these are grounded in the 11 Living Labs in Bulgaria, Canary Islands, Catalonia and Galicia (Spain), Greece, Nouvelle Aquitaine (France), Netherlands-Germany, Norway-Sweden, Portugal, Sardinia (Italy).

What has FIRE-RES achieved in its 1st year?

During this first year, the project focussed on setting the project framework and the thematic lines to build a common understanding of what "fire-resilient landscapes" are. This was done through the organisation of workshops in which the expertise of several actors was consulted. Additionally, an intersectoral working group (the Community of wildfire Innovation) was created to discuss the necessary measures and innovations in the field of forest fires.

To align the organisation of innovation challenges between Living Lab leaders, a training workshop was organised to help address extreme wildfire events in their respective regions. The technical work was also initiated and methodologies regarding fuel mapping to obtain important fuel-related data through earth observation were discussed.

OUR LIVING LABS

This will help improve the reliability of fire simulations, mitigation, and decision-making in at pan-European level, by defining areas where fuel management should be a priority. Thanks to the work done so far, FIRE-RES started to establish the roadmap towards fire-resilient landscapes for the coming years.

What has FIRE-RES accomplished in its 1st year?

FIRE-RES had the opportunity to engage with external actors not only through project workshops but also by taking part in several international events where preliminary results of the project started to be disseminated. During these events, FIRE-RES exchanged information and experiences with other fire-related projects: FirEURisk, Silvanus, FireLogue and TREEADS.

As the project became more visible, two newsletters and a press release were published. In this way, it was possible to focus the attention on the dramatic situation regarding wildfires that Europe had to face this summer. Several wildfires have impacted the FIRE-RES Living Labs. Project partners contributed to the fire management process in Catalonia (Spain), Lesbos (Greece) and Aquitaine (France).

FIRE-RES will continue working on generating new knowledge to manage wildfire events as well as share operational procedures, and good practices among fire management phases and stakeholders

Follow the project on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn

[Find the latest item of news here](#)

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What is SILVANUS about?

SILVANUS is a H2020 Green Deal Innovation Action project, spanning through eighteen countries on four continents, whose main objective is to create an innovative forest management platform to prevent and suppress forest fire by implementing more efficient prevention strategies, quicker detection and response to fire...

...and effective biodiversity restoration, using cutting edge technology (deployment of robots, drones, remote sensing...), detailed stakeholder engagement and policy recommendation based on empirical data.

What are the results of the SILVANUS project so far?

SILVANUS has presented a consolidated overview of the participatory approach carried out with stakeholders on the needs and requirements of forest management authorities, fire fighters, and first responders among others. A historical review of forest fires encountered in previous years across the 12 pilot locations in 11 countries (EU MS, Brazil, Indonesia, Australia) has been made along with an analysis of different forest characteristics models. Measures were considered by the project to meet the Green Deal 2030 objectives.

The first version of the impact assessment framework was presented that will be used for the evaluation of the SILVANUS platform

The first report on the formal specification of sustainable and resilient forest management knowledge model presented the SILVANUS ontology and a metadata index, which will provide a comprehensive search interface to SILVANUS data objects in the platform.

A dissemination strategy with promotional videos, introductory webinars, newsletters, flyers and social media campaigns.

[Detailed results of SILVANUS available here](#)

What TREEADS Project is about?

TREEADS is a large-scale EU Green Deal project which brings together a consortium of 47 partners from 13 European countries and Taiwan in the fight against wildfires.

The TREEADS introduction meeting was held on the 1st of December 2021, followed by a virtual kick-off meeting in February 2022, during which the development of the project was further discussed and consolidated. In May 2022, one month before the physical general assembly meeting in Norway, a technical meeting took place at BAM headquarters in Germany.

Developments and productive discussions of both technical and project management aspects were in the forefront of all the TREEADS consortium meetings. Many workshops were also organized to understand the lifecycle of wildfires. Through them, the forestry, bioeconomy, communities, first responders and stakeholders were engaged and empowered. In the first year of TREEADS life a key wildfire-relevant stakeholder map was also created, a decent number of deliverables were successfully delivered, and the consortium managed to reach many milestones.

What has TREEAD Project achieved in its 1st year?

During this year, TREEADS had the honor of attending and participating in several international dissemination and clustering events along with attracting media attention which spread the TREEADS story further. The project started gaining momentum and pushing out a press release as well as distributing several e-newsletters reinforced that success. A special TV coverage was also filmed on the 1st day of the TREEADS Spanish pilot site visit and is available here. Among other things, a series of interviews was prepared to introduce some of TREEADS consortium experts to the public.

TREEADS managed to establish relationships with the Climate Change & Biodiversity Working Group and the WFRM projects. This way, the partners started networking with other fellow EU funded projects like Firelogue, FireURisk, FIRE-IN, SAFERS, and FireLinks in the battle against wildfires

What has TREEAD Project achieved in its 1st year?

Over the last six months, all partners have collaborated providing expertise and tech insights to the stakeholders and pilots. A large amount of data and methodologies that will be integrated into the TREEADS holistic wildfire management ecosystem are in the process of finalization and a clear and unified vision for Prevention and Preparedness for wildfires in TREEADS is already established.

The structure of the TREEADS Platform, including all the tools that will be developed for the three phases of wildfires has been designed so far and there is progress in showcasing the TREEADS technological solutions for Prevention and Preparedness through a demonstrator that will be developed and integrated into TREEADS platform.

Equally interesting is that a roadmap about the definition and the implementation of the TREEADS wildfire models and services was prepared along with a clear and concrete plan for market analysis and a knowledge hub for TREEADS as part of the “marketplace” of the project. Last but not least, the core development of the project demos will begin based on the TREEADS unified solution architecture that will provide impactful results based on end-users needs.

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What is FirEUrisk Project about?

FirEUrisk is a European Research project aiming to develop an integrated science-based strategy, aggregating knowledge on risk assessment, risk reduction and risk adaptation to tackle the risk of extreme wildfires in Europe. Such fires often lead to loss of human lives, natural resources and economic assets. Their frequency and severity are increasing continuously due to climate change. To manage this situation, it is necessary to assess the biophysical background as well as the socio-economic conditions in the areas prone to wildfires. That is why FirEUrisk involves a variety of actors from different sectors spanning from first responders and researchers to insurance companies, policy makers and citizens.

What is FirEURisk Project about?

1 | Risk assessment Improving preparedness for extreme fires

FirEURisk aims to analyse the **vulnerabilities** of the landscape to extreme wildfires and **mitigate their potential impact**. The project will integrate current **danger monitoring systems** and adapt their output taking into consideration **socio-economic and health factors**.

Physical vulnerabilities of the landscapes, such as fuel load available, temperatures or how prepared houses are.

Socio-economic impacts, with a focus on how the damage of agricultural crops, roads, power lines or water delivery systems in the area would affect the population.

Ecological impacts, such as soil features, water bodies, biodiversity present and surrounding protected areas.

Human drivers of fire, from accidents and arson to land management uses like stubble burning and rural abandonment.

Human health impacts due to air pollution and poor visibility.

Innovative instruments usage, such as satellites, geospatial analysis, meteorological models and social interviews.

Danger estimation of lightning fires and prediction of extreme weather conditions.

3 | Risk adaptation Anticipating future conditions

FirEURisk will estimate how the ongoing **climate and societal changes** will impact extreme wildfires' risk in Europe, to allow the relative areas to adapt accordingly.

Future climate scenarios with expected weather conditions, complemented with projections of possible changes in demography to identify new fire-prone areas.

Future land-use scenarios and their impact, like how abandonment and reforestation will change fuel abundance and composition.

Epidemiological models, to assess the impacts of wildfires on public health in the long term.

Future environment policy models such as the European Union biodiversity strategy and the Green Deal, as well as their effect on extreme wildfire risk.

2 | Risk reduction Tackling the societal factors of fire risk

FirEURisk will consolidate **practical guidelines** to reduce extreme fire risk conditions by evaluating and **harmonising different strategies** that are used around Europe.

Fire policies, such as total fire bans or agricultural uses of fires.

Land management strategies that can reduce wildfire risk, such as prescribed burning, mechanical brush clearing or fuel modification.

Risk reduction trainings for landowners with the support of first responders and experts.

New tools to improve fire response by predicting extreme wildfire behaviour, directed at first responders.

Citizen science apps and websites for public awareness.

Technical solutions to reduce the vulnerability of houses and infrastructures, like non-combustible roof materials or thermal glass for windows.

What is FIRE-IN Project about?

EU-wide collaborative platform for First Responders, researchers and industries

The work in the project is organized in 3 phases: first – the identification of the capability gaps, experienced and expressed by the Fire & Rescue practitioners. The gaps are formulated as challenges to be solved by the research and industry. In the second phase the project partners review ongoing and planned R&D projects and suggest promising solutions, addressing the gaps. During the third phase the project will establish an interactive cooperation with the research and industry and request proposals for the new R&D. The responses will be evaluated by the Associated Experts. Finally the project will provide recommendations for the European Strategic Research and Standardisation Agenda on Security.

Since FIRE-IN Project completed its cycle and produced its results find their newsletter below!

[Click here](#)

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What is FIRElinks Project about?

To accelerating cross-disciplinary communication between fire scientists, with the overall goal to provide for policy makers and land users strong, research-lead foundations that enable implementation of more effective land management approaches

Workplan for the implementation of the COST Action:

MoU objectives and working programme:

1 FIRElinks will develop the EU-spanning network of scientists and practitioners involved in forest fire research and land management with backgrounds such as fire dynamics, fire risk management, fire effects on vegetation, fauna, soil and water, and socio-economic, historical, geographical, political perception and land management approaches.

3 It will connect communities from different scientific and geographic backgrounds, allowing the discussion of different experiences and the emergence of new approaches to fire research.

2 The main aim of FIRElinks is to power synergistic collaborations between European research groups and stakeholders with the objective to synthesize the existing knowledge and expertise, and to define a concerted research agenda which promotes an integrated approach to create fire-resilient landscapes, taking into account biological, biochemical and-physical, but also socio-economic, historical, geographical, sociological, perception and policy constraints. This is an urgent societal need due to expected further intensification and geographical spreading of wildfire regimes under Global Change.

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What is FIRElinks Project about?

Research Coordination

- **Bridging research and communication gaps between different fire researches communities**
- **Coordination of information seeking, identification, collection and/or data treatment**
- **Synthesizing the existing knowledge and data to determine an integrated State-of-the-Art**
- **Standardizations and integration of experiments, measurements, monitoring and interventions**
- **Assessment of models that focus on fire risk, fire behavior, and fire induced landscape changes**

- **Exchange of know-how on fire prevention, firefighting, and post-fire restoration**
- **Involving stakeholders in defining the needs for fire research and coordination of actions**
- **Pan-European web-based database for practitioners, with management strategies/effectiveness and develop a web-based scientific collaboration network, FIRElinksMEDIA**
- **Establish an annual European conference on integrated fire research, a European Society of Fire Research and Management and Exploit a plan through demonstration & dissemination: Technical reports/brochures/ media.**

What is FIRElinks Project about?

Capacity Building

- Harness the experience and expertise in the field of fire research across the diverse European environments to bring together groups of scientists and practitioners working on different aspects of fire
- It is definitive to move forward from studies focussing on specific aspects of the impact of fire on the Earth System to a holistic approach that will underpin effective management strategie

- Streamline and harmonise current research methodologies to assess fire dynamics and effect
- Discussion and cooperation among researchers and practitioners is the basis for new research
- Encourage and facilitate collaboration between scientists and landusers

- Stakeholders and scientists interaction
- Create awareness of the fire issues and attract others to be involved and participate in the Action: Early Career Researchers (ECRs) and practitioners, and scientists from inclusiveness countries
- Form a platform for scientists, practitioners and policymakers
- Transfer to the European society key and basic information about the role of fire and its sustainable and safe management in the Earth System in the 21st Century
- Publish research papers and books to synthesizes the current scientific knowledge and Technical Reports and brochures that will transfers technical information to the land users

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SAFERS in brief.

Forest fires are exacerbated by extreme weather conditions, which are increasing both in frequency and in magnitude due to climate change. Globally, massive fires have swept through forests and other landscapes at an alarming rate, resulting in the loss of human lives, destruction of homes and biodiversity, and emitting millions of tons of CO₂ and other pollutants in addition to various destructive impacts. Therefore, the need of effective management of forest fire emergencies has become very crucial.

To respond to this global challenge, the European Union funded project under the Horizon 2020 programme SAFERS 'Structured Approaches for Forest fire Emergencies in Resilient Societies' is in a mission to support societies becoming more resilient across the key phases of the forests fires emergency management cycle.

SAFERS is going to create an open and integrated platform featuring a forest fire Decision Support System. The platform will use information from different sources: earth observations from Copernicus and GEOSS, fire sensors in forests, topographic data, weather forecasts and even crowdsourced data from social media and other apps that can be used by citizens and first responders to provide situational in-field information.

SAFERS in brief

Such Big Data will be processed using Artificial Intelligence algorithms to generate useful information: risk maps to better plan preparedness actions, early detection of active fires, fire propagation predictions, burned area and fire front delineation, impact assessment estimations, and habitat recovery maps. Moreover, the SAFERS Decision Support System will suggest best practices according to the emergency phase (prevention and preparedness, detection and response, restoration and adaptation) and to the current situation using a semantic knowledge base.

SAFERS project officially started in October 2020 for a period of 3 years (2020-2023) and with a total budget of 3.25 million euros. It is coordinated by LINKS foundation and brings together 14 partners coming from 7 European countries: Italy, Greece, Finland, Germany, United Kingdom, France and Spain.

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We are happy to announce the 1st Joint Dissemination Workshop

Hi there,

You are invited to the First Joint Dissemination Workshop by
EUFireProjectsUnited.

When: Jan 23, 2023

Where: Online

Topic: EUFireProjectsUnited will present their results so far, and after that we will have a fruitful discussion to analyse and understand the difficulties the projects' face, how we can avoid overlaps and more.

After registering, you will receive a confirmation email containing information about joining the workshop.

Looking forward to seeing you!

All the best,
EUFireProjectsUnited

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End of Joint Newsletter

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